

Geology in Motion: The Effects of Warfare on Geology

PART 2

FLOODING

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INTRODUCTION

Local and regional geology has influenced military conflict and operations for millennia. Military strategists often pursue the high ground, and seek to use the terrain to their advantage. Drilling effective water wells and finding suitable building materials are also key components of leveraging geology for military purposes. In addition, many wars have been fought over geologic resources such as fuel, precious metals, and even the land itself. For this series of articles we are focusing on the effects of warfare on the terrain itself. Previously we looked at the scars of bombing left on the landscape, and now we look at examples of strategic flooding. These floods might not preserve an obvious mark on the rock record into the future, but these were catastrophic geologic events that were made possible by the geologic features of the battleground, and were life altering (or life ending) for the locals who were caught in the floods' path.

EXAMPLE 1

1938 Yellow River Flood: Military tactics throughout history have commonly relied on the geography of the surroundings, with many battles determined by the topography. Only occasionally, however, have military strategies involved using the area's geography itself as a weapon, altering the landscape in the process. One such tactic involves flooding rivers to impede operations of the enemy force. Perhaps the most daring, dangerous, and extensive fluvial disruption was the 1938 Yellow River flood in China. This event stands as a stark example of the extensive impact warfare can have on a river system. During the Second Sino-Japanese War, the Nationalist Government of China made the strategic

decision to breach the Yellow River's dikes at Huayuankou in June 1938. This deliberate act was aimed at halting the Japanese advance by creating a defensive barrier, but it also resulted in significant alterations to the landscape. In addition, it also proved deadly to over 500,000 people through drowning and subsequent disease and famine (Lary, 2001).

The Eastern Henan Plain in the lower reaches of the Yellow River has traditionally been prone to flooding and avulsions, prompting the building of levees during the Qing Dynasty (1645-1855) (Zheng et al., 2017, Zue, 1993). In 1855 the river underwent a natural avulsion, diverting to the course shown in Figure 1 (Pai, 2023). This course was then maintained until June 9, 1938, when the Nationalist Army destroyed the Yellow River's south

embankment at Huayuankou in order to impede the progress of the Japanese army.

The immediate consequence of the dike destruction was the inundation of an extensive area across the provinces of Henan, Anhui, and Jiangsu. The flood zone varied in width, but was occasionally as wide as 80 km, and spanned approximately 400 km in length (Figure 1). Around 60% of the villages located in the eastern plains of the Henan province were flooded. Sediment deposition in some areas exceeded 5m in thickness (Pai, 2023). As the Yellow River poured into the valleys of the Jialu and Guo Rivers, it appears that the locals did not have any indications of the incoming flood, and had no time for early evacuation.

FIGURE 1: Map of the Yellow River's current path, the flooded region from 1938-1947, and historical paths. Adapted from Xue, 1993, and Muscolino, 2015.

FIGURE 2: Map of Walcheren Island, depicting the flooding as of October 31, 1944, after the dike breaches were completed. Adapted from canadiansoldiers.com (refer to references and suggested readings).

FIGURE 3: Aerial picture of the breach in the sea dike at Westkapelle after the 3 October 1944 bombardment. Royal Air Force official photographer - <http://media.iwm.org.uk/iwm/mediaLib//9/media-9636/large.jpg> This photograph C 4668 comes from the collections of the Imperial War Museums

The knock-on effects of the breach in the levee and subsequent flood were severe and long-lasting. Erosion widened the initial breach from around 100m to approximately 1460m by 1946. Flooding caused significant changes to the hydrologic system, soil composition, and accessibility of farmland, leading to famine among the flood's refugees. Extensive deposition of sediment from the floods contributed to substantial growth of reeds and subsequent breeding of locusts, affecting an area of over 900 km², which further exacerbated the famine (Pai, 2023). The flood lasted nearly nine years until the restoration work was completed in 1947, artificially restoring the course back to the pre-1938 path. If not for this restorative engineering, the Yellow River would likely still be following this course in the present day.

EXAMPLE 2

The Battle of the Scheldt Estuary - Flooding of Walcheren Island

By September 1944, 5 years into WWII, the Allies recognised the port of Antwerp as being necessary for shortening their logistic lines inland. The German Armed Forces used long-range coastal batteries at Walcheren Island at the headwaters of the estuary to prevent allied ships from reaching Antwerp by sea or minesweeping the waters (Ellis, 1968). Lieutenant-General Guy Simonds commanded The First Canadian Army and planned for the deliberate breaching of the dikes surrounding Walcheren using RAF Bomber Command aerial bombardments from 3-11 Oct 1944 (Copp, 2007). In the most simplistic description, the

dikes were reinforced dunes that surrounded the island, somewhat akin to an atoll (Figure 2). The breaches resulted in the inundation of Walcheren lowgrounds with seawater, leading to significant geological changes, particularly in sedimentation of fields and erosion of the water channels at the breach sites. Seawater rushed in, carrying marine sediments that were deposited across the flooded areas. This sudden influx of marine sand and silt altered the soil composition, transforming fertile agricultural land into saline, futile ground. The new layer of marine sediment also changed the physical landscape that required extensive remediation efforts to regain its agricultural viability (Goodlet, 2013).

Walcheren's waterways were also dramatically changed. The broken dikes created new

FIGURE 4: Image of the Möhne Dam after the attack, showing the damage to the dam, as well as debris in the foreground. Image credit: By Bundesarchiv, Bild 101I-637-4192-20 / Schalber / CC-BY-SA 3.0, CC BY-SA 3.0 de, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=5413163>.

paths for the seawater to flow, carving out new channels and widening existing ones. These changes rearranged the island's fluvial landscape, including both temporary and permanent waterways. Rivers and streams, like the River Scheldt, were forced to change their courses, which impacted the local geography and required adjustments to water management strategies (Goodlet, 2013).

Towns and cities across the island faced unique challenges. Vlissingen's harbor was clogged with sediment that required extensive dredging for port operations. In Westkapelle, where the dikes were initially breached, new water channels and sediment deposits required major reconstruction efforts. The historic town of Veere faced similar issues with siltation in its harbor and waterways, disrupting its role as a local trade center. Middelburg, the capital of Zeeland, dealt with the indirect effects of altered water flow and sedimentation in surrounding agricultural lands, prompting necessary adjustments to local water management infrastructure (Goodlet, 2013).

The task of restoring Walcheren after the war was immense. Dredging was crucial to clear out the clogged channels and restore navigability and drainage (Goodlet, 2013). The saline soil needed to be treated to restore fertility to the land. Essential dikes were rebuilt to protect the island from future flooding. New water management practices were implemented to adapt to the altered water flow patterns and ensure effective drainage. These combined geologic and engineering efforts were vital to

return Walcheren back to its pre-war state and to secure its long-term sustainability.

EXAMPLE 3:

Dambusters Raid: Allied forces in WWII identified the dams of the Ruhr Valley in Germany as a strategic military target, as these dams were used to generate hydroelectric power and as a fresh water source for steelmaking. Anticipating this threat, the German Armed Forces installed nets to prevent torpedoes from reaching the dam. To evade the nets, the allies invented a barrel-shaped bomb that they could drop from a modified Lancaster bomber aircraft. The bomb was designed to skip on the water over the nets, then strike the dam wall and sink to the bottom before exploding.

The Dambusters raid, officially named Operation Chastise, significantly changed the landscape of the Ruhr Valley. When the Möhne, Eder, and Sorpe dams were breached, a massive volume of water was suddenly released downstream, where almost 1300 people were killed from the flooding (Adamo et al., 2020). The powerful floodwaters swept away soil, rocks, and plants, causing extensive erosion along riverbanks and riverbeds that were deposited further downstream.

The heavy load of deposited sediment and debris changed sedimentation patterns and created new landforms like sandbars and silt deposits. These changes had a lasting impact on regional agriculture and infrastructure, where fertile farmland was buried under

sediment and transportation routes were disrupted.

In addition to the impact of erosion and deposition on landforms, the floodwaters altered the natural courses of rivers. The force of the water carved out new channels and widened existing ones, permanently changing the geomorphology of the river system. These new channels disrupted the existing flow patterns and created challenges for water management and flood control.

The floodwaters also inundated wide areas of the floodplain, creating temporary lakes and ponds. These water bodies gradually drained or evaporated, leaving behind layers of fine-grained sediment. This further altered the local topography and contributed to the region's evolving landscape. The changes in water flow and sediment deposition also affected the region's ecology, disrupting biological habitats for fish and other aquatic organisms.

The destruction of infrastructure was another significant consequence of the floods. Bridges, roads, and buildings along the rivers were heavily damaged or destroyed, adding to the debris carried by the floodwaters. This debris further influenced the changes in the river systems, making the recovery effort even more challenging.

The Dambusters raid caused dramatic and long-lasting changes to the Ruhr Valley. The combination of erosion, deposition, and channel alteration reshaped the landscape in ways that were felt long after the immediate aftermath of the floods.

CONCLUSION:

Reclamation projects in the aftermath of these strategic floods limit the lasting geologic evidence of these events, but each of them highlights the powerful and far-reaching effects that human actions, even in war, can have on the natural environment. The combined effects of these battles have flooded plains, altered the course of rivers, deposited widespread sediment, and limited production of energy. In addition to the effects these floods have on the landscape, there is the additional human element to these battles. In the immediate aftermath of the 1938 Yellow River flood, between 38,000 and 89,000 civilians drowned. In the years that followed, it is estimated that up to 500,000 more civilians died from subsequent famine, disease, and drowning. Operation Chastise is estimated to have killed approximately 1300 civilians. Given these devastating effects to people and the environment, the Geneva Conventions were amended in 1977 to prevent attacks on dams and dikes. The next installment of this series will look at examples of how warfare has affected sedimentology.

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